

TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF FUNGAL RHINITIS AND ALLERGIC RHINITIS

Rasulova Kibriyo Abdurakhman's daughter

Assistant Professor of Physiology
Samarkand State Medical University

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Abstract. *Fungal diseases (mycoses) is a pathological condition of the organism, caused by the vital activity of microorganisms (fungi) parasitizing the skin and mucous membranes of humans and animals. This article focuses on the peculiarities and some related issues to this subject and relates it to humans.*

Keywords: *symptoms, signs, treatment, prevention, allergic rhinitis, fungal rhinitis.*

Fungal diseases and allergic rhinitis are common form of infectious diseases in everyday life. In this article it is discussed that these types of diseases and their symptoms, consequences and the steps to take in the situation of occurrence. In medicine, there is a classification of fungal diseases. Thus, according to this classification several types of pathology are distinguished which are as follows:

Keratomycosis (various colored lichen, scurvy mycosis, Piedra);

Dermatophytes (trichophytosis, microsporia, favus, epidermophytosis of the chovy layers, foot mycosis);

Candidiasis (spreads to the surface, skin and mucous membranes; generalized, South American, Busse-Bushke, Gilchrist candidiasis, keloid blastomycosis);

Deep (chromomycosis, sporomycosis, histoplasmosis, coccidiosis, mycetoma);

Pseudomycoses (erythrasma, actinomycosis).

However, in most countries of the world, the classification of fungal diseases according to the localization of the pathological process is accepted, according to which diseases are classified as follows:

Tinea pedis - foot mycosis;

Tinea corporis - mycosis of the smooth skin of the body;

Tinea cruris - chow mycosis;

Tinea capitis - mycosis of the hairy part of the head;

Tinea unguim — onychomycosis (nail fungus);

Tinea manum - wrist mycosis;

Tinea barbae - mycosis of the face.

CAUSES OF FUNGAL DISEASE

There are two types of fungi groups that will be observed with the causes to be triggered. Filamentous structures or dermatomycetes (trichophyton, microsporon, achorion) are often observed. The second group of fungi are yeasts belonging to the genus Candida. Disease sources are infected animals or people. Infection occurs through close contact with a defective part of the human or animal body, as well as through contact with contaminated items of the patient. Since fungi multiply in the external environment with very stable spores, they fall on everyday objects, epidermis or other areas of mucous membranes and remain there for a long time. There is a risk of getting infected with fungal diseases when visiting beauty salons, hairdressers, swimming pools,

baths, manicure salons. There are cases of excessive sweating (hyperhidrosis), decreased immunity, skin rashes and cracks, avitaminosis and non-observance of personal hygiene. Likewise, when it is infected, this shows some signs of it in several ways. In the next paragraph it is explained and discussed thoroughly.

SYMPTOMS

Usually, all fungal diseases begin with a light and imperceptible itching of the skin. However, there are several ways to illustrate them which distinguishes according to the type of fungi. Each type is characterized by certain symptoms:

Keratomycosis affects the epidermis, does not cause inflammation, is characterized by itching of damaged dermatomes, changes in pigmentation. Lesions have different sizes and shapes.

Dermatophytes — in which the epidermis and its excesses are involved, there is a possibility of the development of an inflammatory process. Legs, hair, skin layers are characterized by excessive itching or redness, cracks, moisture are formed. Focal alopecia, changes in the color and thickness of the nails are observed.

Candidiasis - white foci appear, under which redness is detected. It may be accompanied by pain or itching.

Deep mycosis is a systemic, massive damage to the skin and internal organs, accompanied by the disseminated spread of fungi throughout the body. The nature of the course can be acute or chronic.

It is advisable to take emergency and necessary immediate measures in which it is noticed that fungi are infected. If such signs are present, it is necessary to consult a dermatologist. The recovery process will be as follows in steps:

Causes of disease

Symptoms of allergic rhinitis

Diagnostics

Treatment of allergic rhinitis

Diet

Dangerous aspects

Risk group

Prevention

See all doctors who treat allergic rhinitis

The other issue which is going to be discussed along with fungi is allergy which is called rhinitis. Allergic rhinitis is a disease of the upper respiratory tract, caused by an allergic reaction in the body. This disease is often seasonal (if there is an allergy to pollen). Rhinitis can be acute or chronic. It is observed while the cause of it is got in contact with the patient. As other diseases rhinitis is caused by several factors which are going to be discussed separately. Rhinitis occurs due to swelling of the nasal mucosa. The main causes of the disease are allergens, the most common of which are plant pollinators, dust, pet dander, chemicals, drugs, and fungi. This disease is passed from generation to generation. In children, this disease occurs due to weakened immunity. They will be vulnerable to causes of the disease and easily affected with it. In terms of symptoms of the disease, there several of them which can be noticed easily with an eye. Allergic rhinitis is characterized by the following symptoms:

flu;

runny nose;

frequent sneezing;
tickling sensation in the throat;
continuous coughing attacks;
itchy eyes, increased tearing;
increased sensitivity of eyes to light;
loss of sense of smell;

If you find that you have similar symptoms, contact your doctor immediately. It is easier to prevent the consequences of the disease than to eliminate it. Allergic reactions can get even worse if time passes and the symptoms can easily turn into a real affect of the disease. It is easier and more practical if the patient with allergic symptoms is observed by a doctor on time. In terms of diagnostics, to determine the method of treatment, the allergist-doctor, after conducting a general examination and listening to the patient's complaint, prescribes the following tests and analyses:

general analysis of blood;
immunogram;
laboratory examination of mucus secreted from the nose;
rhinoscopy;
provocative skin tests to determine the cause of allergies.

Treatment of allergic rhinitis

Recovering from the disease includes several steps to take. Treatment of allergic rhinitis includes:

immunotherapy;
antihistamine drugs;
vasoconstrictor drugs;
cell membrane stabilizers;
glucocorticosteroids;
therapeutic exercises;
inhalation.

Conclusion

From the discussed issues and details above, what can be inferred is that some common diseases like fungi and allergic rhinitis can be noticed and diagnosed easily by people themselves with their symptoms and effects. This article informs about them and tells what kinds of precaution steps should be taken in order to eliminate the effect and fully get recovered. It is not advised to wait for long, but to go to the doctor immediately not to worsen the situation by allowing a symptoms to turn into a dangerous form of its disease.

REFERENCES

1. Alimova O. B. Comparative Clinical and Laboratory Parameters for Various Forms of Hemolytic Disease of the Newborn //Scholastic: Journal of Natural and Medical Education. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 238-241.
2. Расулова К. А., Насретдинова М. Т. ҲАЛҚУМДАГИ ЗАМБУРУҒЛИ ЗАРАРЛАНИШНИНГ САМАРАЛИ ДАВОЛАНИШИНИ БАҲОЛАШ //Биология ва тиббиёт муаммолари. – 2022. – №. 2. – С. 135.

3. Ашуров З. Ш., Усербаева Р. К. Влияние тревожности и депрессии у матерей на эффективность воспитания подростков, основанного на технике повышения осознанности (mindfulness). – 2022.
4. Abdurakhman qizi, R. K. (2023). Treatment and Prevention of Otitis or Ear Inflammation. Scholastic: Journal of Natural and Medical Education, 2(5), 322–325.
5. Rakhimova, M. (2022). INFERTILITY IN WOMEN CLASSIFICATION, SYMPTOMS, CAUSES AND FACTORS, RECOMMENDATIONS FOR WOMEN. Science and innovation, 1(D7), 245-250.
6. Rakhimova, M. (2023). DISORDER OF THE MENSTRUAL CYCLE CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, CLASSIFICATION, TREATMENT METHODS. Science and innovation, 2(D2), 31-37.
7. Alimova O. B. Comparative Clinical and Laboratory Parameters for Various Forms of Hemolytic Disease of the Newborn //Scholastic: Journal of Natural and Medical Education. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 238-241.
8. Расулова К. А., Насретдинова М. Т. ҲАЛҚУМДАГИ ЗАМБУРУҒЛИ ЗАРАРЛАНИШНИНГ САМАРАЛИ ДАВОЛАНИШИНИ БАҲОЛАШ //Биология ва тиббиёт муаммолари. – 2022. – №. 2. – С. 135.
9. Ашуров З. Ш., Усербаева Р. К. Влияние тревожности и депрессии у матерей на эффективность воспитания подростков, основанного на технике повышения осознанности (mindfulness). – 2022.
10. Abdurakhman qizi, R. K. (2023). Treatment and Prevention of Otitis or Ear Inflammation. Scholastic: Journal of Natural and Medical Education, 2(5), 322–325.
11. Насретдинова М. Т., Хайитов А. А. ВЫБОР ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ПОДХОДА ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ КИСТ ВЕРХНЕЧЕЛЮСТНОГО СИНУСА //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 1.
12. Худайбердиева Ч. К., Таджиев Б. М., Алимова О. Б. КЛИНИКО-ИММУНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОСТРОЙ ДИАРЕИ У ДЕТЕЙ С СИНДРОМОМ ГЕМОКОЛИТА // " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2022. – С. 196-197.
13. Бабаева Н. и др. Оценка метаболических изменений в развитии пролонгированной неонатальной гипербилирубинемии //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4/С. – С. 807-812.
14. Mannonovna, R. M. (2023). TORCH INFECTION: DANGER FOR PREGNANT WOMEN, PERIOD OF EXAMINATION. Science and Innovation, 2(2), 57-58.
15. Shodiyeva D., Shernazarov F. ANALYSIS OF THE COMPOUNDS PROVIDING ANTIHELMITIC EFFECTS OF CHICORIUM INTYBUS THROUGH FRACTIONATION //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D2. – С. 64-70.
16. Насретдинова М. Т., Хайитов А. А. ВЫБОР ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ПОДХОДА ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ КИСТ ВЕРХНЕЧЕЛЮСТНОГО СИНУСА //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 1.
17. Худайбердиева Ч. К., Таджиев Б. М., Алимова О. Б. КЛИНИКО-ИММУНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОСТРОЙ ДИАРЕИ У ДЕТЕЙ С СИНДРОМОМ ГЕМОКОЛИТА // " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2022. – С. 196-197.

18. Бабаева Н. и др. Оценка метаболических изменений в развитии пролонгированной неонатальной гипербилирубинемии //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4/S. – С. 807-812.